

DOPPELSEMIGROUPS AND THEIR UPFAMILY EXTENSIONS

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In the talk we shall discuss the algebraic structure of doppelsemigroups and their upfamily extensions. By definition, a *doppelsemigroup* is an algebraic structure (D, \dashv, \vdash) consisting of a non-empty set D equipped with two associative binary operations \dashv and \vdash satisfying the following axioms:

$$(D_1) \quad (x \dashv y) \vdash z = x \dashv (y \vdash z),$$

$$(D_2) \quad (x \vdash y) \dashv z = x \vdash (y \dashv z).$$

If (D, \dashv, \vdash) is a doppelsemigroup, then rearranging the parentheses in an expression that contains only operations \vdash , \dashv and elements of D do not change the result. A doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) is called *commutative* [6] if both semigroups (D, \dashv) and (D, \vdash) are commutative. A doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) is said to be *strong* [7] if it satisfies the axiom

$$x \dashv (y \vdash z) = x \vdash (y \dashv z).$$

In [2], the task of describing all pairwise non-isomorphic (strong) doppelsemigroups with at most three elements has been solved. We proved that there exist 8 pairwise non-isomorphic two-element doppelsemigroups among which 6 doppelsemigroups are commutative. All two-element doppelsemigroups are strong. It was proved that there exist 75 pairwise non-isomorphic three-element doppelsemigroups among which 41 doppelsemigroups are commutative. Non-commutative doppelsemigroups are divided into 17 pairs of dual doppelsemigroups. Also up to isomorphism there are 65 strong doppelsemigroups of order 3, and all non-strong doppelsemigroups are not commutative. In [3], we studied cyclic doppelsemigroups. A doppelsemigroup (G, \dashv, \vdash) is called a *group doppelsemigroup* if (G, \dashv) is a group. A group doppelsemigroup (G, \dashv, \vdash) is said to be *cyclic* if (G, \dashv) is a cyclic group. It was proved that up to isomorphism there exist $\tau(n)$ finite cyclic (strong) doppelsemigroups of order n , where τ is the number of divisors function. There exist infinite many pairwise non-isomorphic infinite cyclic (strong) doppelsemigroups.

A family \mathcal{M} of non-empty subsets of a set X is called an *upfamily* if for each set $A \in \mathcal{M}$ any subset $B \supset A$ of X belongs to \mathcal{M} . By $v(X)$ we denote the set of all upfamilies on a set X . Each family \mathcal{B} of non-empty subsets of X generates the upfamily $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle = \{A \subset X : \exists B \in \mathcal{B} (B \subset A)\}$. An upfamily \mathcal{F} that is closed under taking finite intersections is called a *filter*. A filter \mathcal{U} is called an *ultrafilter* if $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{F}$ for any filter \mathcal{F} containing \mathcal{U} . The family $\beta(X)$ of all ultrafilters on a set X is called the *Stone-Čech compactification* of X , see [5]. An ultrafilter $\langle \{x\} \rangle$, generated by a singleton $\{x\}$, $x \in X$, is called *principal*. Each point $x \in X$ is identified with the principal ultrafilter $\langle \{x\} \rangle$ generated by the singleton $\{x\}$, and hence we can consider $X \subset \beta(X) \subset v(X)$. It was shown in [1] that any associative binary operation $*$: $S \times S \rightarrow S$ can be extended to an associative binary operation $*$: $v(S) \times v(S) \rightarrow v(S)$ by the formula

$$\mathcal{L} * \mathcal{M} = \left\langle \bigcup_{a \in \mathcal{L}} a * M_a : \mathcal{L} \in \mathcal{L}, \{M_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{L}} \subset \mathcal{M} \right\rangle$$

for upfamilies $\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M} \in v(S)$. In this case the Stone-Čech compactification $\beta(S)$ is a subsemigroup of the semigroup $v(S)$.

In [4], it was shown that the upfamily extension $(v(D), \dashv, \vdash)$ of a (strong) doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) is a (strong) doppelsemigroup as well. Also we introduced the upfamily functor v in the category **DSG** of doppelsemigroups and their homomorphisms and showed that this functor preserves strong doppelsemigroups, doppelsemigroups with left (right) zero, doppelsemigroups with left (right) identity, left (right) zeros doppelsemigroups. On the other hand, the functor v does not preserve commutative doppelsemigroups and group doppelsemigroups. It was proved that the automorphism group of the upfamily extension of a doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) of order $|D| \geq 2$ contains a subgroup, isomorphic to $C_2 \times \text{Aut}(D, \dashv, \vdash)$. Also we described the structure of upfamily extensions of all two-element doppelsemigroups and their automorphism groups.

References

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